

SUPPLEMENTARY INSTRUCTIONAL MATERIAL IN BREAD AND PASTRY PRODUCTION IN THE ACHIEVEMENTS OF THE SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

This study aimed to know the relationship between the supplementary instructional material and the performance of the senior high school students in bread and pastry production. The study was conducted in College of Sciences, Technology and Communications, Inc., Sariaya, Quezon the respondents were composed of forty-one (41) grade 11 senior high school students of Home Economics strand. It sought to determine the demographic profile of the respondents, perceived the supplementary instructional materials in terms of learning objectives, learning content, activities, assessment, design/layout, and clarity of material, the respondents' achievements in terms of written and activities and the significant relationship between perceived supplementary instructional materials and achievements of students in Bread and Pastry Production. This study used descriptive correlational research design, instrument used was a questionnaire, and statistical tool employing weighted mean and Pearson-Product-Moment, correlation coefficient. Purposive sampling was used to select the sample respondents and virtually administered. Findings revealed that there is no significant relationship between the supplementary instructional material and the achievements of the senior high school students in bread and pastry production in terms of activities and written. Based from the results, since the interpreted results on all variables under instructional material does not conformed with the correlation significant of 0.01 level on both activities and written, the overall result states that there is no significant relationship between the perceived supplementary instructional material and the achievements of the students in bread in pastry production. The researcher recommends to have a more in-depth research regarding the supplementary instructional materials. The researcher recommend that the future researcher made another research study regarding to the same variables of the study or to any variables that could show the relationship of the variables. Since we are in the new normal set up of education, the researcher encourages the provision and improvisation of instructional materials as a necessary to make lessons interesting available to the students. Continuous enhancement of the supplementary instructional materials and teachers guide is necessary to be able to improve the achievements of the students in TLE Bread and Pastry Production. Further research in supplementary instructional materials is necessary, since we are facing the new learning and teaching process that is caused by the changes made by the pandemic we are facing.

Keywords: Home Economics, bread and pastry production, supplementary instructional materials.